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MYRTUS: A preliminary Assessment of the Heterogeneous Computing Continuum Infrastructure

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This work was supported by MYRTUS project, funded by the European Union by grant No. 101135183. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This manuscript is a preprint of a paper submitted for publication in Applied Reconfigurable Computing (ARC 2026), Lecture Notes in Computer Science, Springer. The final authenticated version is expected to be published by Springer.

Please, cite this paper as follow:

Juan Encinas, Francesco Ratto, Marco Fois, Alfonso Rodríguez, Veena Rao, Luca Castello, Maria Katuscia Zedda, Claudio Rubattu, Andrés Otero, Francesca Palumbo. "MYRTUS: A preliminary Assessment of the Heterogeneous Computing Continuum Infrastructure", 2026, Applied Reconfigurable Computing. Architectures, Tools, and Applications. ARC 2026. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19557725>.

MYRTUS: A preliminary Assessment of the Heterogeneous Computing Continuum Infrastructure

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Abstract. The increasing diffusion of cyber-physical systems and Internet of Things applications demands computing infrastructures capable of handling large data volumes under strict latency, scalability, and energy constraints. Traditional cloud-centric approaches are often inadequate for such requirements, motivating the adoption of the computing continuum paradigm, which integrates edge, fog, and cloud resources. This paper presents a preliminary assessment of the MYRTUS project, a Horizon Europe initiative aimed at enabling seamless orchestration across heterogeneous computing infrastructures. The MYRTUS architecture combines a distributed infrastructure, an AI-driven orchestration engine, and a dedicated development environment to support adaptive applications. A demonstrator based on UAV navigation in GPS-denied environments is introduced to evaluate the infrastructure. The application distributes processing tasks across continuum layers, leveraging edge devices for real-time operations and cloud resources for intensive computation. Results highlight the potential of MYRTUS to support efficient, scalable, and energy-aware execution of complex distributed applications.

Keywords: Computing Continuum · Edge Computing · UAV Navigation · Container Orchestration · FPGA.

1 The MYRTUS Project

The growing deployment of cyber-physical systems (CPS) and Internet-of-Things (IoT) systems generates large volumes of data that require continuous processing with strict constraints on latency, scalability, energy efficiency, and privacy. Traditional centralized cloud computing often fails to meet these requirements, especially for real-time applications. As a result, research has moved toward the *computing continuum*, which integrates edge, fog, and cloud resources to dynamically distribute workloads. However, orchestrating such heterogeneous infrastructures remains challenging due to fragmentation, interoperability limitations, and diverse hardware and software platforms.

The MYRTUS project⁷ (Multi-layer 360°dYnamic orchestration and interopeRable design environmenT for compute-continUum Systems) is a Horizon Europe initiative that aims to address these challenges by developing technologies that enable the seamless integration, orchestration, and design of distributed systems across the computing continuum [2]. The project aligns with the objectives of the European EUCloudEdgeIoT (EU-CEI) initiative, which promotes the development of interoperable and sovereign digital infrastructures that combine cloud, edge, and IoT technologies.

Beyond the integration of distributed computing resources, MYRTUS envisions the evolution of cyber-physical systems toward a *living dimension*, where digital and physical components continuously interact, adapt, and cooperate with human users. In such systems, distributed components are capable of learning from their environment, dynamically adapting their behavior, and coordinating with other agents in a decentralized manner. This vision requires infrastructures capable of supporting highly distributed, heterogeneous, and adaptive computing environments.

To realize this vision, the MYRTUS architecture is structured around three main technological pillars:

- *Computing Continuum Infrastructure*, which provides the underlying distributed infrastructure integrating heterogeneous computing resources across the edge–fog–cloud continuum.
- *MIRTO Cognitive Engine*, an AI-driven runtime orchestration framework responsible for dynamic workload distribution and system adaptation across infrastructure layers.
- *Design and Programming Environment (DPE)*, a development environment that supports the modeling, analysis, and deployment of distributed applications targeting heterogeneous continuum infrastructures.

Together, these pillars provide a comprehensive framework for the design, deployment, and management of distributed applications across heterogeneous infrastructures [1]. The project is currently in Month 27, midway through its second implementation phase.

⁷ <https://myrtus-project.eu/>

This presentation focuses on the MYRTUS reference architecture and introduces a preliminary demonstrator designed to assess the capabilities and potential of the infrastructure developed within the project.

2 Computing Continuum Infrastructure in MYRTUS

The MYRTUS infrastructure is organized as a layered architecture that integrates heterogeneous computing resources across three main levels: edge, fog, and cloud. These layers collectively form an *onion-like* computing continuum in which resources are composable and interconnected, enabling seamless execution of distributed computational workflows.

A key feature of the MYRTUS infrastructure is its ability to integrate heterogeneous computing resources. The system is designed to support a wide range of hardware platforms, including general-purpose processors, hardware accelerators, reconfigurable architectures, and specialized computing units. This heterogeneity enables the infrastructure to adapt to different performance and energy requirements. For instance, computationally intensive tasks can be assigned to high-performance cloud resources, while latency-sensitive operations can be executed at the edge. Additionally, hardware specialization allows certain workloads, such as artificial intelligence inference, to be executed efficiently using dedicated accelerators.

The infrastructure also supports a composable resource model, where computing nodes from different providers can be federated and orchestrated as part of a unified system. This approach improves flexibility and scalability while reducing dependency on specific vendors.

3 A preliminary demonstrator: Vision-based navigation in GPS-denied environments

This section describes an application developed to demonstrate how a realistic industrial scenario can exploit the capabilities of the MYRTUS cloud–edge computing continuum infrastructure. The selected use case focuses on the navigation of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) in GPS-denied environments.

Small UAV often need precise position updates in places with a lack of GPS satellite signals (i.e., along narrow streets with tall buildings, across valleys, or in areas with deliberate interference). In these scenarios, the ground becomes the only reliable reference: roads, roofs, and field boundaries form a stable visual aid that does not depend on external infrastructure. The challenge is to read that information quickly and reliably from a moving device with limited energy budgets and strict latency requirements.

A common approach to solving this problem relies on a downward-facing camera to provide a continuous stream of visual information, and feature extraction and matching algorithms to process that stream, identifying specific structures in the image that can be used to infer the UAV’s position. The method is deliberately simple: convert each frame into a set of distinctive indicators (i.e.,

Fig. 1. UAV image-to-map matching pipeline (images from the real application).

features), search for those indicators on a prepared map, and deduce the position when a consistent set of correlations is detected. This approach, shown in Figure 1, is both low-cost and scalable.

The processing pipeline associated with visual navigation typically includes three main stages: feature extraction, feature description, and feature matching. Feature extraction identifies distinctive keypoints in the captured image, such as corners or textured patterns. Feature description then generates compact numerical representations of these keypoints that capture the structure of their surrounding regions. Finally, feature matching compares descriptors between images to identify corresponding points and estimate the geometric relationship between them. Once a sufficient number of correspondences is identified, algorithms such as RANSAC can estimate the transformation between the images, allowing the UAV to determine its relative position within the environment.

This application represents an ideal candidate for deployment across the MYRTUS computing continuum. Certain stages of the processing pipeline, such as feature extraction and initial filtering, can be performed directly on edge devices integrated within the UAV platform. These edge implementations can leverage energy-efficient hardware accelerators such as FPGA-based architectures to achieve real-time performance while minimizing power consumption. Intermediate processing tasks can be offloaded to nearby fog nodes when additional computational resources are required, enabling collaborative processing across multiple nodes. Meanwhile, cloud resources can be used for large-scale data storage, map generation, and model training tasks that require significant computational power.

To do so, a feature-extraction and matching pipeline has been developed and evaluated using the two-cluster architecture developed according to the MYRTUS principles, and shown in Figure 2. The experimental setup consists of two Kubernetes clusters connected via Ligo. Each cluster contains nodes corresponding to the three layers of the continuum: one cloud-layer node featuring a vast resource FPGA, one fog-layer node with moderate resources, and four edge-level nodes optimized for low-power operation.

Fig. 2. Representation of the two-cluster architecture used for validation. The master nodes that run the Liqo processes are highlighted in green.

4 Conclusions

By distributing computation across multiple layers of the infrastructure, MYRTUS enables efficient execution while respecting constraints related to latency, bandwidth, and energy consumption. The UAV use case illustrates how heterogeneous resources across the continuum can cooperate to support complex real-time applications. More broadly, this approach demonstrates how computing continuum infrastructures can support emerging intelligent systems that must operate across highly dynamic and resource-constrained environments.

The MYRTUS project represents an important step toward realizing a unified computing cohigh-capacity FPGA, one fog-layer node with moderate resources, and four edge-layering heterogeneous hardware platforms, intelligent orchestration mechanisms, and advanced development tools, MYRTUS enables the deployment of distributed applications capable of adapting to changing conditions and resource availability. The vision-based UAV navigation use case highlights the practical benefits of this approach, illustrating how complex workloads can be distributed across multiple infrastructure layers to achieve both high performance and energy efficiency. The results of this work contribute to the broader European effort to build interoperable digital infrastructures capable of supporting next-generation cyber-physical systems and data-driven services.

Acknowledgments. The work have been conducted within the MYRTUS project, funded by the European Union, by grant No. 101135183. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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